

Approach to derive a Net Ecosystem Productivity indicator

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The approach to estimate net ecosystem productivity (NEP, the negative of net ecosystem exchange or NEE) is based on the empirical relation between gross primary productivity (GPP) estimated from the Fluxnet stations' network and GPP estimated by MODIS products and other spatially explicit environmental covariates (see Table 1). The NEP indicator is concluded by including the relation of ecosystem respiration (RECO) and monthly average temperature.

The dataset comes from the Fluxnet network stations with croplands which have grown wheat (Figs. 1 and 2), and remote sensing (RS) products. The spatialisation is done by relating spatially-explicit RS to the Fluxnet measures.

Fig1. Fluxnet stations used for the indicator estimation.

Variable	Definition	Description
GPPF18	8-day sum of GPP Fluxnet	Calculated
GPPMOD8	8-days sum of GPP MODIS	From raster
prWC	Monthly precipitation	From worldclimate
tmaxWC	Monthly maximum temperature	From worldclimate
tminWC	Monthly minimum temperature	From worldclimate
tyyyy	Year of the data point	NA
tmm	Month of the data point	NA
tdd	Day of month of the data point	NA
tymon	Month and year of the data point	NA
site	Fluxnet site code	NA
moist.avg.t	8-days average soil moisture	From raster
NEEF18	8-day sum of NEE Fluxnet	Measured
period8d	Number of 8-day period in the year of the data point	NA
tavgWC	Monthly average temperature	Calculated from tmax/tmin

Below a summary of the main data set variables is shown:

```
summary(my.stations.GPP)

##      order      GPPF18      temp      pr
## Min.   : 1.00   Min.   : 0.000   Min.   : -161.68   Min.   : 0.00
## 1st Qu.: 95.75   1st Qu.: 2.675   1st Qu.: 38.34    1st Qu.: 5.24
## Median :210.50   Median : 9.993   Median : 88.70    Median : 12.31
## Mean   :231.69   Mean   : 26.387   Mean   : 85.73    Mean   : 17.50
## 3rd Qu.:360.25   3rd Qu.: 36.374   3rd Qu.: 132.53   3rd Qu.: 23.44
## Max.   :630.00   Max.   :177.921   Max.   : 278.08    Max.   :187.60
##      GPPMOD8      prWC      tmaxWC      tminWC
## Min.   : 0.00   Min.   : 1.50   Min.   : -7.00    Min.   : -15.000
## 1st Qu.: 3.50   1st Qu.: 35.90   1st Qu.: 9.00    1st Qu.: 1.000
## Median :15.50   Median : 56.40   Median :16.00    Median : 6.000
## Mean   :21.18   Mean   : 64.03   Mean   :15.59    Mean   : 6.334
## 3rd Qu.:35.10   3rd Qu.: 83.70   3rd Qu.:22.00    3rd Qu.: 12.000
## Max.   :92.40   Max.   :282.10   Max.   :40.00    Max.   : 24.000
##      timeform      tyyyy      tmm      tdd
## Length:3600      Min.   :2001   Min.   : 1.000   Min.   : 1.00
## Class :character  1st Qu.:2006   1st Qu.: 4.000   1st Qu.: 9.00
## Mode  :character  Median :2008   Median : 7.000   Median :16.00
##                                     Mean   :2008   Mean   : 6.588   Mean   :15.61
##                                     3rd Qu.:2011   3rd Qu.: 9.000   3rd Qu.:24.00
##                                     Max.   :2014   Max.   :12.000   Max.   :31.00
##      tymon      site      moist.avg.t      NEEF18
## Length:3600      Length:3600      Min.   :0.04713   Min.   : -102.054
## Class :character  Class :character  1st Qu.:0.18397   1st Qu.: -12.467
## Mode  :character  Mode  :character  Median :0.22269   Median : 2.839
##                                     Mean   :0.22575   Mean   : -5.132
```

```

##                               3rd Qu.:0.26291   3rd Qu.:   9.845
##                               Max.    :0.36725   Max.    :  50.438
##   period8d   tavgWC
##   Min.      : 1   Min.      : -11.00
##   1st Qu.   :12   1st Qu.   :  5.00
##   Median    :23   Median    : 11.00
##   Mean      :23   Mean      : 10.96
##   3rd Qu.   :34   3rd Qu.   : 17.00
##   Max.      :45   Max.      : 32.00

```

It can be seen from Figs. 3-8 that the relationship between C fluxes and temperatures have optima, so an only-linear model is not appropriate

Fig3. Relation between GPP and minimum temp.

Fig4. Relation between GPP and max temp.

Fig5. Relation between GPP and average temp.

Fig6. Relation between NEE and min temp.

Fig7. Relation between NEE and max temp.

Fig8. Relation between NEE and avg temp.

Relation with 8-days average soil moisture is noisy, but strong

Fig9. Relation between GPP and soil moisture.

Fig10. Relation between -NEE and soil moisture.

Data for year, Fluxnet station and even times of the year a bit heterogeneous, but a low and high period can be distinguished based on the number of 8-d periods (Figs 11-15).

Fig11. Relation between Fluxnet GPP and MODIS GPP per day of month.

Fig12. Relation between Fluxnet GPP and MODIS GPP per month of year.

Fig13. Relation between Fluxnet GPP and MODIS GPP per year.

Fig14. Relation between Fluxnet GPP and MODIS GPP per periods of 8 days in a year.

Fig15. Relation between Fluxnet GPP and MODIS GPP per station.

So with all this info, we can build a model for GPP:

An initial model with the max and min temps with their polynomial element:

```
my.gpp.m4.tmaxmin$call

## lm(formula = GPPF18 ~ GPPMOD8 + prWC + tmaxWC + I(tmaxWC^2) +
##      tminWC + I(tminWC^2) + moist.avg.t, data = my.stations.GPP)
```

and the results can be seen here

```
anova(my.gpp.m4.tmaxmin)

## Analysis of Variance Table
##
## Response: GPPF18
##           Df Sum Sq Mean Sq  F value    Pr(>F)
## GPPMOD8     1 2197996 2197996 3870.7259 < 2.2e-16 ***
## prWC        1    101     101    0.1770  0.673989
## tmaxWC      1   60056   60056  105.7605 < 2.2e-16 ***
## I(tmaxWC^2) 1    3746   3746    6.5972  0.010254 *
## tminWC      1    483    483    0.8499  0.356631
## I(tminWC^2) 1    5122   5122    9.0205  0.002688 **
## moist.avg.t 1   13469  13469   23.7196 1.162e-06 ***
## Residuals 3592 2039721    568
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
```

```
summary(my.gpp.m4.tmaxmin)

##
## Call:
## lm(formula = GPPF18 ~ GPPMOD8 + prWC + tmaxWC + I(tmaxWC^2) +
##     tminWC + I(tminWC^2) + moist.avg.t, data = my.stations.GPP)
##
## Residuals:
##      Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
## -80.166 -10.300  -2.364   7.949 119.229
##
## Coefficients:
##              Estimate Std. Error t value Pr(>|t|)
## (Intercept)  15.61028    2.98635   5.227 1.82e-07 ***
## GPPMOD8       1.39795    0.02788  50.148 < 2e-16 ***
## prWC          0.04085    0.01241   3.291 0.001009 **
## tmaxWC       -1.00277    0.37532  -2.672 0.007578 **
## I(tmaxWC^2)   0.02843    0.01285   2.212 0.027010 *
## tminWC        0.03673    0.28080   0.131 0.895937
## I(tminWC^2)  -0.06980    0.02061  -3.386 0.000717 ***
## moist.avg.t -40.94293    8.40669  -4.870 1.16e-06 ***
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## Residual standard error: 23.83 on 3592 degrees of freedom
## Multiple R-squared:  0.5279, Adjusted R-squared:  0.527
## F-statistic: 573.8 on 7 and 3592 DF,  p-value: < 2.2e-16
```

when compared to the simplest model(GPP Fluxnet = GPP MODIS), and other models

```
my.gpp.m6.min$call
## lm(formula = GPPF18 ~ GPPMOD8, data = my.stations.GPP)
```

the complete model works better:

```
AIC(my.gpp.m6.min,my.gpp.m4.tmaxmin)
##           df      AIC
## my.gpp.m6.min      3 33188.59
## my.gpp.m4.tmaxmin  9 33057.04
```

So it might be the one to use for two periods as said before (it is not perfect as the data are strongly heteroscedastic, but at least is something), a winter very low one and a pre-harvest high one.

The models work worse for NEE, an example here (lower R^2)

```
anova(my.nee.m1.tmaxmin)
## Analysis of Variance Table
##
## Response: NEEF18
##           Df  Sum Sq Mean Sq  F value    Pr(>F)
## GPPMOD8      1  535537   535537 1289.1443 < 2.2e-16 ***
## prWC          1   27414    27414   65.9909 6.167e-16 ***
## tmaxWC        1  131875   131875  317.4483 < 2.2e-16 ***
## I(tmaxWC^2)   1     214     214    0.5156  0.4728
## tminWC        1   12991    12991   31.2728 2.409e-08 ***
## I(tminWC^2)   1   10519    10519   25.3218 5.090e-07 ***
## moist.avg.t   1   20842    20842   50.1699 1.689e-12 ***
## Residuals    3592 1492191     415
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
```

```
summary(my.nee.m1.tmaxmin)
##
## Call:
## lm(formula = NEEF18 ~ GPPMOD8 + prWC + tmaxWC + I(tmaxWC^2) +
##     tminWC + I(tminWC^2) + moist.avg.t, data = my.stations.GPP)
##
## Residuals:
```

```
##      Min      1Q  Median      3Q      Max
## -99.817 -7.446  1.589  10.503  68.058
##
## Coefficients:
##              Estimate Std. Error t value Pr(>|t|)
## (Intercept) -14.608579   2.554275  -5.719 1.16e-08 ***
## GPPMOD8     -0.901781   0.023843 -37.822 < 2e-16 ***
## prWC        0.001052   0.010619   0.099 0.92107
## tmaxWC      1.395257   0.321014   4.346 1.42e-05 ***
## I(tmaxWC^2) -0.055421   0.010991  -5.042 4.83e-07 ***
## tminWC      0.729322   0.240171   3.037 0.00241 **
## I(tminWC^2) 0.098495   0.017632   5.586 2.49e-08 ***
## moist.avg.t 50.929991   7.190380   7.083 1.69e-12 ***
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## Residual standard error: 20.38 on 3592 degrees of freedom
## Multiple R-squared:  0.3313, Adjusted R-squared:  0.33
## F-statistic: 254.3 on 7 and 3592 DF,  p-value: < 2.2e-16
```

New additions

An update to the model for avoiding the use of correlated variables (mainly max and min monthly temperature), we can use a linear multiple regression model that uses only average temperature (average between max and min monthly temperatures). This is the final model suggested in the cookbook.

```
summary(my.gpp.m1.3.tavg.tvgsq.moistsq.rd)
##
## Call:
## lm(formula = GPPF18 ~ GPPMOD8 + tavgWC + I(tavgWC^2) + moist.avg.t,
##     data = my.stations.GPP)
##
## Residuals:
##      Min      1Q  Median      3Q      Max
## -81.773 -10.165  -2.441   8.227 119.712
##
## Coefficients:
##              Estimate Std. Error t value Pr(>|t|)
## (Intercept) 10.098346   2.097793   4.814 1.54e-06 ***
## GPPMOD8     1.394339   0.027428  50.837 < 2e-16 ***
## tavgWC     -0.359390   0.167160  -2.150 0.031624 *
## I(tavgWC^2) -0.017945   0.006048  -2.967 0.003025 **
## moist.avg.t -27.167827   7.444934  -3.649 0.000267 ***
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
```

```
##
## Residual standard error: 23.88 on 3595 degrees of freedom
## Multiple R-squared: 0.5255, Adjusted R-squared: 0.525
## F-statistic: 995.5 on 4 and 3595 DF, p-value: < 2.2e-16
```

The approach in Fluxnet to derive ecosystem respiration (RECO) uses the partitioning of NEE into GPP and Reco. Such partitioning is based on the temperature sensitivity of RECO, as defined by Lloyd and Taylor (1994, *Funct.Ecol.*), and proposed by Reichstein (2005, *GCB*). We cannot use the same approach as it is based on a model that defines a variable temperature independent component of respiration (called R_{ref} , and dependent on factors other than temperature such as ecosystem plant functional types, etc.). This Fluxnet approach to RECO cannot be related to spatially explicit environmental covariates in a intuitive way as for GPP.

A summary of RECO is provided below.

```
summary(my.resp2$rate)
##      Min.   1st Qu.   Median     Mean   3rd Qu.    Max.
##  0.1723   8.3902  16.4339  21.0294  29.3010 105.3481
```

It was noted though that the relationship between temperature and RECO from the Fluxnet stations dataset constitutes a process similar as those modelled by thermal performance curves (Fig16). In such models metabolic rates are modelled based on temperature only, in a similar way to the Lloyd and Taylor (1994) approach.

Reco Fluxnet and monthly average temperature

Fig16. Relation between RECO and temperature.

Fig17. Relation between RECO and temperature per station.

Thus, in order to derive an independent estimate of Reco that is at the same time practical for the cookbook (this is, it does not depend on additional remote sensing products or additional datasets so that partners can apply it easily), Reco was modelled by thermal performance curves using the R package rTPC. We focused on models with few simple parameters that define optimal and extreme temperature values after removing a clear outlier of the Reco dataset.

Fig18. Relation between RECO and temperature as modelled by different thermal performance models. Blue= Deutsch, red= Lactin2, violet = Lrf, pink= Modified Gauss, brown = Ratkowsky, green = Weibull models.

This allow us to predict a NEE for each of several models tested, by subtracting the model's predicted respiration from the Fluxnet GPP. With this preliminary predicted NEP value, the model performance was evaluated by looking at the relationship between the preliminary NEP vs observed NEP and also looking at the value of their RMSEs.

Fig19. Relation between preliminary predicted (as calculated from models results of RECO) and observed NEP.

This allowed us to decide to use a Modified Gauss' model. The model has the following form:

$RECO = RECO_{max} * e^{-0.5((tavg - tavg_{opt})/a)^b}$, $RECO_{max}$ is maximum RECO at optimum average monthly temperature, $tavg_{opt}$ is optimum average monthly temperature, a is a shape parameter related to the width of the curve, and b is other shape parameter that allows asymmetrical fitting. The values of the parameters' estimates for the dataset are: $a = 5.99$, $b = 1.14$, $RECO_{max} = 38.86$, and $tavg_{opt} = 18.39$

One of the last test is to estimate the goodness of fit between our NEP

indicator (calculated from our estimated GPP with the final model, and with RECO) with NEP observed. This is the relationship between $NEP_{pred} = GPP_{pred} - RECO_{pred}$ and -NEEF18.

Fig20. Relation between predicted NEP (with our GPP and RECO models) and observed NEP.

Fig21. Relation between predicted NEP and observed NEP. Red line linear regression line, blue line is the 1:1 line.

```
summary(my.nep.final)

##
## Call:
## lm(formula = (-1) * my.nep.ind$NEEF18 ~ my.nep.ind$NEPpred)
##
## Residuals:
##      Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
## -75.832  -9.807  -1.760   7.209  97.266
##
## Coefficients:
##              Estimate Std. Error t value Pr(>|t|)
## (Intercept)      1.0333     0.3515    2.94 0.00331 **
## my.nep.ind$NEPpred  0.7605     0.0178   42.72 < 2e-16 ***
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## Residual standard error: 20.29 on 3597 degrees of freedom
## Multiple R-squared:  0.3366, Adjusted R-squared:  0.3364
## F-statistic: 1825 on 1 and 3597 DF,  p-value: < 2.2e-16
```

, and a RMSE of

```
nep.sep.rmse
## [1] 20.78691
```

As it can be seen, the final NEP indicator is close to the 1:1 line, but it has a low R^2 as other factors not accounted for might be at play, particularly at high NEP values.

A comparison with a reduced linear model deriving NEP from using all environmental covariates shows that the previous NEP model should be preferred. This is because the predicted NEP from the linear model has a poorer performance, particularly at low NEP values when $RECO > GPP$ (the relationship seems not to be even linear).

```
## Warning in abline(my.nep.allcovs.red, col = "red"): only using
the first two of 6 regression coefficients
```


Fig22. Relation between predicted NEP with environmental covariates and observed NEP. Red line linear regression line, blue line is the 1:1 line.

Summary of the NEP model fitted with environmental covariates:

```
summary(my.nep.allcovs.red)
##
## Call:
```

```

## lm(formula = (-1) * NEEF18 ~ GPPMOD8 + prWC + tavgWC + moist.avg.t +
##     I(moist.avg.t^2), data = my.stations.GPP)
##
## Residuals:
##      Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
## -70.603 -10.484  -1.665   7.793 100.024
##
## Coefficients:
##              Estimate Std. Error t value Pr(>|t|)
## (Intercept)    1.01592    4.54334   0.224  0.8231
## GPPMOD8         0.90633    0.02234  40.568 <2e-16 ***
## prWC          -0.02179    0.01007  -2.164  0.0305 *
## tavgWC        -1.25511    0.06783 -18.503 <2e-16 ***
## moist.avg.t    47.83237   38.12853   1.255  0.2097
## I(moist.avg.t^2) -197.02242  80.37490  -2.451  0.0143 *
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## Residual standard error: 20.49 on 3594 degrees of freedom
## Multiple R-squared:  0.3239, Adjusted R-squared:  0.323
## F-statistic: 344.3 on 5 and 3594 DF,  p-value: < 2.2e-16

```

, and a RMSE of

```

nep.dir.rmse
## [1] 20.47489

```

So even if the models are similar in R^2 and RMSEs, the model derived from GPP and RECO separately is preferred.

One way to explore to improve the model could be including soil variables known to affect soil CO₂ flux, and/or using a generalised additive modelling (gam) approach (a preliminary test showed much higher fits for GPP, but the application of gam models is not practical for a cookbook).

An appendix with an example of the acquisition of data in R, and the fitting of a thermal performance model is given.